

Determination of fenitrothion in water samples by spectrometry using new reagents iminodibenzyl and 4-amino-5-hydroxy-2,7-naphthalene disulfonic acid

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Simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods for the determination of fenitrothion in either pure form or in its formulations are described. The methods are based on the diazotization of reduced fenitrothion followed by coupling with alcoholic iminodibenzyl (IDB) in acidic medium to give a purple coloured product having a λ_{\max} of 575 nm (first method) or coupling with 4-amino-5-hydroxy-2,7-naphthalene disulfonic acid monosodium salt (AHND) to produce red color product with λ_{\max} of 523 nm (second method) at pH 11.5. Both the methods are highly reproducible and have been applied formulations and in water samples. The proposed methods have been applied successfully for the determination of fenitrothion residues in water samples upto the ppb level with the preconcentration on Amberlite XAD-4.

Fenitrothion (*o,o*-dimethyl-*o,p*-nitro-3-methylphenyl phosphorothionate) belongs to an organophosphorus pesticide, extensively applied on crops. Due to indiscriminate application, it finds a way into surface water bodies, through agriculture runoff and municipal waste water systems by ingestion and inhalation. Finally, it reaches the human system. Many methods have been developed for the determination of fenitrothion¹. The spectrophotometric methods based on the using diazotization in the presence of oxidising agents and its metabolites by various alkaline hydrolysis of the pesticides have been determined².

We propose a new simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of fenitrothion based on the interactions with two new reagents i.e. iminodibenzyl (IDB), to produce purple colored product in acidic medium or 4-amino, 5 hydroxy-2,7-naphthalene disulphonic acid mono sodium salt (AHND) to produce red color product in basic medium. The methods offer the advantages of sensitivity, selectivity and rapidity without the need for extraction.

Results and discussion

The reduced fenitrothion was diazotized with IDB in acidic medium to form purple coloured product (λ_{\max} 575 nm) and also coupled with AHND in buffer medium to get red coloured product (λ_{\max} 523 nm). These wavelengths were used for all measurements.

It was found that 1% solution of NaNO_2 in the range of

1–3 ml, a 2% solution of sulfamic acid in the range of 1–3 ml, 2–4 ml of 0.5% alcoholic IDB and 3–5 ml of alcohol were necessary to achieve maximum color intensity. In case of AHND method, 1–2 ml of 1% sodium nitrite, 1–2 ml of 2% sulfamic acid, a 0.5% AHND in the range of 0.5–2 ml and 3–8 ml of buffer of pH 11.5 were added to get maximum color intensity. The effect of volume of buffer (pH 11.5) on color formation of fenitrothion was shown in Fig. 1. In both methods, the excess of nitrite could be removed by the addition of sulfamic acid and has no effect on absorbance values. The favourable results were obtained by using 1 : 1 sulfuric acid in IDB method for dilution compared to other acids and solvents. In case of fenitrothion coupled with AHND method, the colour solution with different solvents like water, methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile and 1,4-dioxan have been tested. The result showed that water gives maximum stability and offers good intensity of the color.

Beer's law is obeyed over the pesticide concentration range of 0.4 to 16 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for IDB and 0.4–9.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for AHND as coupling reagents. The upper limit of the Beer's-Lambert range is determined by a plot of absorbance against concentration at the value of λ_{\max} . Beyond this limit, the correlation results were affected. Hence, the measurements were excluded above these limits to keep the linear relationship. The optical characteristics and the precision data are shown in Table 1.

In an acidic medium nitrite reacts with reduced

fenitrothion to form diazonium salt. The salt is then coupled either with IDB in presence of ethanol to yield a purple colored product with λ_{\max} of 575 nm or with AHND in presence of buffer of pH 11.5 to give a red colored product with λ_{\max} of 523 nm. The reaction mechanism for the formation color products are shown in Scheme 1.

The diazotization of reduced fenitrothion is completed in 5 min at room temperature. The stability of the purple colored product formed from fenitrothion-IDB interaction is one hour.

After this time interval, the color intensity fades slowly. Attempts were made to increase this time interval by altering the reaction conditions, but unsuccessful. However, a time interval of 1 h was sufficient enough to record the absorbance measurements. In contrast, the red product formed by the coupling reaction between fenitrothion and AHND were stable for 6 days. An increase of temperature from 0°C to room temperature did not affect the results in both the methods. However, a temperature of about 30°C is recommended for both the methods and reproducible statistical results were obtained.

Table 1. Optical characteristics and precision data

Parameters	AHND	IDB
Colour	Red	Purple
λ_{\max} (nm)	523	575
Stability	6 days	1 h
Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.4–9.0	0.4–16.0
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.2888	0.1316
Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.0962	0.0438
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	0.219×10^5	0.303×10^5
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.0131	0.00937
Optimum photometric range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.8–6.0	0.8–14.0
Regression equation (Y^n)		
Slope (β)	-0.04541	0.0792
Intercept (a)	-0.0013	0.0136
Correlation coefficient (R^b)	0.9939	0.9933
Relative standard deviation RSD 10 ^c	1.1269	0.7889
Range of error \pm	± 1.59	± 1.08
$Y^n = bx + a$		

where x = conc. in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, $n = 10$, $c = 10$ triplicate.

Under diazotization reaction conditions used, the effect of foreign species and other pesticides on the determination of fenitrothion were studied. Known amounts of variety of foreign species and pesticides were added to a standard solution containing 50 μg of fenitrothion in 10 ml and the solutions were analysed by the proposed method. The results obtained are shown in Table 2. The results show that the foreign species of pesticides analysed with fenitrothion the proposed method indicates the validity of the method for the determination of fenitrothion.

Table 2. Determination of fenitrothion in presence of excipients (conc. of fenitrothion 30 $\mu\text{g}/10$ ml)

Sl. no.	Foreign species	Tolerance limits ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)
1.	Ca^{2+}	200
2.	Mg^{2+}	200
3.	Cu^{2+}	300
4.	Al^{3+}	400
5.	NH_4^+	300
6.	CO_3^{2-}	250
7.	SO_4^{2-}	150
8.	Cl^-	300
	<i>Other pesticides :</i>	
	BHC	150
	Carbofuran	100
	Quinolphos	200
	Malathion	300
	Diazinon	250
	Ethion	200
	Dialdrin	200

The effect of additives, solvents and emulsifiers associated with the fenitrothion in its formulations were investigated using the developed methods. The methods does not suffer any interference from common excipients and other substances. The analysis of interference with the excipients was conducted from the initial step that is the reduction stage. However, the ratio of excipients and the active ingredients in the pesticide really does not matter.

The reproducibility of the method was checked out by 10 replicate determinations at the 6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level of the pesticide for IDB 4 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level of pesticide for AHND. The relative standard deviation found between 0.76 and 1.1. The applicability of the proposed methods for the assay of commercial formulations was studied. The results are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Determination of fenitrothion in formulations 50% emulsion

Amount of pesticide active ingredient taken	Found ^a by proposed method		Reported method ³
	AHND	IDB	
50 μg	49.3 \pm 0.80	49.2 \pm 0.81	48.9 \pm 0.95

^aAverage of the five determinations \pm relative standard deviation (%).

Determination of fenitrothion in water samples :

The methods were applied to the determination of fenitrothion residues in spiked water samples. The results relating to the recoveries of fenitrothion residues from spiked water samples are shown in Table 4. The percentage recoveries of the fenitrothion in water sample ranges from 98.18 to 99.55%. The results showed that fenitrothion residues upto 0.4–16 μg in IDB method 0.4–9.0 μg can be determined from 2 litres of water samples with a relative standard deviation for IDB 0.7889 for AHND 1.269.

Conclusion :

The proposed methods have several advantages over reported method³ in the literature. The present methods are fast, simple, economical, selective and has lower limit of detection. The statistical parameters and the recovery study data clearly indicate the better reproducibility, smaller sample and reagent consumption.

The results obtained in Tables 3 and 4 indicate the developed fenitrothion-IDB and fenitrothion-AHND procedure provide quite good sensitivity, precision and sample throughout require for routine analysis, quality control laboratories, water systems and other environmental studies. Besides the use of Amberlite XAD-4 resin system used for preconcentration offers the possibility of better determination of fenitrothion using spectrophotometry.

Table 4. Recovery of fenitrothion residues from spiked water samples

Sl. no	Added ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Found ⁿ proposed method		Reported method ³
		AHND	IDB	
1.	0.8	0.783 \pm 0.80	0.781 \pm 0.75	0.778 \pm 0.05
2.	1.6	1.553 \pm 0.90	1.556 \pm 0.80	1.550 \pm 0.07
3.	2.4	2.353 \pm 0.90	2.354 \pm 0.75	2.348 \pm 0.09
4.	3.2	3.118 \pm 0.80	3.119 \pm 0.70	3.109 \pm 0.80
5.	4.0	3.920 \pm 0.70	3.923 \pm 0.80	3.910 \pm 0.09

n = 5 Average value \pm relative standard deviation %.

Analysis of the commercial formulations containing fenitrothion showed no interference from common excipients.

Fig. 1. Effect of buffer (pH 11.5) on the fenitrothion-AHND reaction.

Experimental

Apparatus : A HITACHI U-2001 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer with stoppered 10 mm matched glass cells was employed under the conditions recommended by the instrument manufacturer. The flow system consisted of a glass column was filled with Amberlite XAD-4 resin upto a height of 10 cm with 20 mm i.d. The ends of the tube were fitted with cotton to retain the resin in the tube. The column was washed successively with 50 ml of methanol, dimethylether and double distilled water.

Materials and vessels used for trace analysis were kept in 10% nitric acid for at least 48 h and subsequently washed three times with distilled water before use.

Note

Reagents and solutions : All chemicals used were of analytical grade and double distilled water employed throughout the experiment. 0.1228 g of 95% fenitrothion was dissolved in 100 ml of methanol (Rallis India Ltd., Bangalore, India). For preparing 50% emulsifiable concentration 24.4 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of fenitrothion into 100 ml of methanol. A 10 ml aliquot of the stock solution was diluted upto the mark with methanol to get working standard solution.

A 0.5% solution of freshly prepared IDB (Sigma, USA) in alcohol and AHND (Merck, Germany) solution of 0.5% (0.5 g AHND in 5 ml of concentrated HCl and diluted to 100 ml with water) was employed. The 1% aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (B.D.H.), 2% aqueous solution of sulfamic acid, 1 : 1 sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide-phosphate buffer of pH 11.5 were used for the experiment.

Accurately weighed 100 mg fenitrothion was transferred into a 100 ml beaker containing 4 ml of methanol, 0.5 of zinc dust and 4 ml of concentrated HCl were added and the mixture is left for 30 min to reduce from nitro group to amino group. The solution was filtered and transferred to a 100 ml standard flask and made up to the mark. The working standard solution of reduced fenitrothion containing 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared by further dilution.

Procedure : Aliquots of the working standards of reduced fenitrothion (10–300 $\mu\text{g IDB}$, 10–200 $\mu\text{g AHND}$) were transferred into 25 ml calibrated flask. For IDB method, 2 ml of 1% NaNO_2 is added, cooled to 0°C and added 2 ml of sulfamic acid cooled followed by addition of 3 ml of 0.5% alcoholic IDB along with 4 ml of alcohol, left for 3 min and diluted to the mark with 1 : 1 sulphuric acid. After mixing the solution thoroughly, the absorbance was measured at 575 nm against the corresponding reagent blank within one hour and the calibration graph was constructed. For AHND method 1 ml of 1% sodium nitrite was added, cooled to 0°C and 1 ml of 2% sulfamic acid was added. The solution was swirled followed by addition of 1 ml of 0.5% AHND and 4 ml of phosphate buffer of pH 11.5. The solution was brought into room temperature and kept the solution on water bath for 5 min and then cooled at room temperature, diluted to the mark with water, and mixed well. The absorbance was measured at 523 nm against the corresponding reagent blank and calibration graph was constructed.

Procedure for the assay of fenitrothion in commercial formulations : An amount equivalent to 50 mg of fenitrothion was taken. The experiments was carried out by the aforesaid procedure. The fenitrothion in its formulation was determined either by IDB method or by AHND method.

Recovery of fenitrothion from spiked water samples : Spiked water samples were prepared by adding known amounts of fenitrothion formulations 10 to 300 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in 2 liters each of pesticide free water and then allowing them to stand over night.

A glass column was filled with Amberlite XAD-4 resin upto a height of 10 cm, the column was washed successively with 50 ml of methanol, dimethyl ether and double distilled water. Then the spiked water was allowed to percolate through the column at the average rate of 5 ml per minute. When all the water was passed through the column was allowed to drain for 10 min. The tap was closed and about 100 ml diisopropyl ether was added to the column and left for 10 min. After this time, the column were drained into 250 ml beaker, the solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in 10 ml of methanol and the pesticide content was determined by the procedure described above.

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